

Correction Factors for Mode II Interlaminar Toughness Tests (ELS and ENF)

by

Y.Wang and J.G.Williams

Mechanical Engineering Department
Imperial College of Science, Technology and Medicine
London, SW7 2AZ

Abstract

In fracture toughness calculations of beam specimens, various forms of corrections for conventional beam theory are proposed. This report investigates the form of correcting the crack length a by a length χh , where h is the half thickness. χ is a constant which depends on the elastic parameters of the material. The predictions using this correction are compared with results using several numerical schemes and those of experiments using the end notch flexure (ENF) test configuration.

1. Introduction

Mode II delamination fracture toughness tests are commonly carried out on end notch flexure (ENF) and end loaded split (ELS) specimens which behave as slender beams. However it has long been known that the use of simple beam theory to determine energy release rate can lead to significant errors. Kanninen [1] solved the problem for the Mode I double cantilever beam (DCB) test by modeling the beam roots as beams on an elastic foundation to give both root rotation and shear deformation. A very accurate result was obtained for an isotropic material by correcting the crack length a by the addition of a length equal to $0.67h$, where h is the thickness of one arm. However for delamination tests of composites materials although the beams are usually slender but the shear modulus is lower

relative to the axial (flexural) modulus than the isotropic case and there is a correspondingly larger correction needed to a . It has been shown [2] that Kanninen's solution can be extended to this case making a correction of χh where χ is a function of the elastic moduli and is strongly dependent on shear modulus. Typical values for χ are 2.5. The solution has given rise to an experimental correction procedure in which the compliance (C) is measured and since C is proportional to a^3 a plot of $C^{1/3}$ vs $(a+\chi h)$ will give the correction factor. This has proved most successful [3] and is likely to be part of the standard method. Mode II tests are also important for composites since G_{IIC} is often different from G_{IC} . Fig.1 shows two testing geometries, the ELS and ENF tests which are discussed in detail in [4]. Beam theory is particularly important for their analysis since they are both prone to instability (particular the ENF test) and other methods of calculating G are not possible. Some consideration of corrections for the ENF test [4] has been made but not in the form of the χh correction to a . Since the method is likely to be used in mode I, the application of the method to Mode II test was investigated numerically by the authors [5] and proven to be successful. The ENF tests of Mode II are therefore carried out and the method of processing the experimental data is discussed.

2. Method of Analysis

In the DCB test the expression for χ from the beam on an elastic foundation model gave [2],

$$\chi = \sqrt{\frac{1}{18K} \left(\frac{a_{66}}{a_{11}} \right) \left[3 - 2 \left(\frac{\Gamma}{1+\Gamma} \right)^2 \right]^{1/2}} \quad (1)$$

where a_{11} , a_{22} and a_{66} are the elastic compliances and K is a function of Poisson's ratio and is approximately 0.85.

$$\Gamma = \frac{1}{K} \frac{a_{66}}{\sqrt{a_{11} a_{22}}}$$

and models the effect of transverse stretching of the beam root. For the mode II tests the compliance expressions are (for ELS specimens)

$$C = \frac{3(a+\chi h)^3 + (L+2\chi_0 h)^3}{2Bh^3 E_{11}} \quad (2)$$

and (for ENF specimens)

$$C = \frac{3(a+\chi h)^3 + 2(L+\chi_0 h)^3}{8Bh^3E_{11}} \quad (3)$$

where L , h and a are defined in Fig.1, B is the width and $E_{11}=1/a_{11}$ is the axial modulus. χ_0 is the correction applied to the beam length L . For ELS test it is similar to the DCB test so that χ_0 is expected to be similar to the value of DCB tests, except that the beam rests on a rigid foundation. For the ENF test the correction is now only from shear and does not include rotation and so would be expected to be less than for the DCB. χ models the deformation at the crack root when the beams are bent in the same sense, as opposed to the DCB where they are in opposite senses, and would also be expected to be less. Attempts to model this case were not successful other than the conclusion that χ should be approximately half that of the DCB test, i.e. replacing 18K by $4 \times 18K = 61.5$.

In ref.[5] ABAQUS finite element programme was then used to calibrate equation (1) and the best fitting of the results was decided. The final result was then compared with the value of G_{II} deduced from;

$$G_{II} = \frac{P^2}{2B} \frac{dC}{da}$$

and that calculated from the numerical analysis. Since G_{II} is not commonly computed, it was decided to use several methods to ensure accuracy.

3. Numerical Results

In ref.[5] the ELS test was explored with a given set of elastic constants and fixed L , and then changing crack length a . The computed values of C are given in Table.1. The compliance for $a=0$, C_0 is also computed and the correction factor χ can be calculated from;

$$C-C_0 = \frac{3(a+\chi h)^3}{2Bh^3E_{11}} \quad (4)$$

and these are shown in Table.1.

G_{II} was calculated for three of these cases by four methods. In the first the values for

C were curve fitted with a polynomial in order to find dC/da . In the second the J contour integral was used. The accuracy of compliance and J-integral is justified by using very fine mesh. There was a slight tendency for J to decrease with increasing size of contour but variations were very small, the difference of J values (ignoring the first contour value which is the least accurate, see [6]) between the second contour and the last contour is 0.45% as shown in Table.2. The third method is crack closure [7] in which the crack tip is released and the fourth is by computing C for a and $a+0.5$ (mm) and finding $\Delta C/\Delta a$. Good agreement between these methods are obtained as it is shown in Table.4.

Table.3 gives the results for χ of keeping $a=20$. (mm) and changing the elastic constants. A least squares fitting method was then used to fit equation (1) to these values and this gave $18K=63$; i.e.

$$\chi = \sqrt{\frac{1}{63} \left(\frac{a_{66}}{a_{11}} \right)} \left[3 - 2 \left(\frac{\Gamma}{1+\Gamma} \right)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

and these values are also shown in Table.3 and difference from the computed values is always less than 10%. Table.1~3 also include χ_o values deduced from C_o and compared with the values calculated from equation (1) with $18K=11$ (ref.[2]). As expected the agreement is good indicating that the total compliance could be used to find G_{II} or to determine E_{11} as a crosscheck.

Finally in both Table.1 and Table.3 G_{II} is calculated from the corrected expression for dC/da and the χ values from equation (5);

$$G_{II} = \frac{9(a+\chi h)^2}{4B^2 h^3 E_{11}} P^2 \quad (6)$$

and from the contour integral method. The differences are generally less than 4% and compared favourably with variations from the different numerical schemes.

For the ENF test a similar analysis was performed and the results were summarised in Table.5. From equation (3) we have:

$$C - C_o = \frac{3(a+\chi h)^3}{8Bh^3 E_{11}} \quad (7)$$

for which χ may be computed and

$$G_{II} = \frac{9P^2(a+\chi h)^2}{16B^2h^3E_{11}} \quad (8)$$

The values in the first set of results are the same as those in [4] and the χ values are seen to agree closely with that from equation (5). The G_{II} values from the contour integral and equation (8) again agree closely. The second set of results use the same parameters as the ELS test and similarly good agreement is achieved. The final set of results includes varying a_{66} and demonstrates that equation (5) and (8) give an accurate prediction. The χ_o values are also given and those in the last set are compared with equation (1). The values are not well represented by equation (1) and this is because the correction for L in the ENF test is mostly due to shear and the form of the χ_o correction is not appropriate. Corrections of the form given in [4] are probably more appropriate. However for calculating G_{II} via load only the χ correction is satisfactory.

4. Experimental Results

A number of tests are carried out using ENF configuration so that comparison could be made between the numerical and the experimental results. The specimens made of unidirectional carbon/peek (APC2) sheet (thickness $2h = 3.12\sim 3.22$ mm), which is considered to have orthotropic material behaviour. Specimens were cut into beams with the total length about 200.0 (mm) and the width 20.0 (mm). An aluminium foil was embedded at the centre line of the beam thickness to form an initial crack. The distance of the total span $2L$ between the two roller supporters is fixed as 100.0 (mm). The material properties of APC2 are normally $E_{11} = 115\sim 130$ (GPa), $G_{12} = 5.0$ (GPa), $E_{22} = 10.0$ (GPa), therefore the correction factor χ can be estimated by Equation (5) giving $\chi=0.7$.

During the tests, the compliance C_o is first measured by using the crack-free portion of the specimen. By shifting the beam position a various compliance values at different crack length can be obtained. Twelve tests are performed and the results are given in Table.6.

Using the compliance data from these tests, the correction factor can be calculated by using a proper curve fit method. From the FE analysis, it is understood that in ENF tests, the correction for crack length a by the form of $(a+\chi h)$ is satisfactory, but not for the beam length $2L$. However it is observed that the ENF test is basically a three-point bending test with very little unsymmetric behaviour, hence the correction for the beam length $2L$ can be estimated by merely taking account of the shear effect, as given in [4]. The compliance equation then takes the form of

$$C = \frac{1}{8E_{11}Bh^3} \left[2L^3 + 2.4Lh^2 \frac{E_{11}}{G_{12}} + 3(a+\chi h)^3 \right]$$

For APC2, the ratio of $R = E_{11}/G_{12}$ is usually about 25, then the compliance equation can be written as

$$C = x(1) \left[2L^3 + 2.4RLh^2 + 3(a+x(2)h)^3 \right]$$

where $x(1)$ is the beam flexibility factor $1/(8E_{11}Bh^3)$ and $x(2)$ is the correction factor χ . A least square fitting method is used to optimise $x(1)$ and $x(2)$ from the compliance data of the experiments. This analysis gives E_{11} between 118~130 (GPa) for all specimens, and the results for χ are listed in Table.6. It shows that most χ values are between 0.4~1.0, which indicate that the correction factor in the form of $(a+\chi h)$ by Equation (5) is of the right order, but to obtain accurate results, very careful measurement of the compliance of specimens is vital because of the form of the dependence of C on a . Some negative χ values are also observed which are the consequence of inaccurate measurements. This scheme gave much more consistent results than the $(C-C_0)^{1/3}$ vs a method.

5. Conclusions

The numerical results show conclusively that applying the χ correction to a gives accurate values for G_{II} via the load and that χ can be computed from equation (5). This is true for the ELS and ENF tests. Such a correction is preferable to those methods in [4] since it is geometry independent.

If the elastic parameters are not known then, in principle, χ can be found experimentally by plotting $(C-C_0)^{1/3}$ versus a as described in [3] for Mode I tests. However, in the latter, it is $C^{1/3}$ which is used and here there is an accuracy problem since the compliance difference is used. The problem is illustrated in [3] where ELS compliance data is analysed assuming that $\chi_0 = \chi$ for a/L in the range 0.4 - 0.8. The χ values agreed quite well with the mode I values while examination of the data in Table.1 would suggest that an average somewhere between χ and χ_0 would be expected though generally near χ_0 which is approximately that of the mode I test. It seems likely that inadequate clamping of the specimen base made χ_0 high thus giving the good agreement noted. The values of G_{II} so calculated were high having been corrected by too high a value of χ .

The difficulty is that G_{II} is determined by a , and hence χ , while the compliance is strongly influenced by L , and hence χ_0 . It is thus very difficult to determine accurately a value of χ from compliance measurement; a problem which is common in many fracture tests

specimens where numerical stress intensity factors are used. The best procedures here would seem to be either to calculate χ from equation (5) if a various moduli are known or can be estimated. Alternatively the values of E_{11} can be taken from mode I tests and χ scaled down by a factor of $(11/63)^{1/2} = 0.42$.

This is probably preferable since effective χ values can be higher than those calculated because of crack front curvature and microcracks. Obviously the direct determination from $(C-C_0)$ is the best if sufficient accuracy can be achieved.

References

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Table.1 Compliances by FEA (ELS specimen)

Computations: B=1.0 (mm) h=1.0 (mm) L=60.0 (mm) P=1.0 (N)

$$a_{11}=6.8 \times 10^{-3}(\text{GPa})^{-1}, a_{22}=128. \times 10^{-3}(\text{GPa})^{-1}, a_{66}=362. \times 10^{-3}(\text{GPa})^{-1}$$

$$\nu_{12} = 0.3$$

$$C_0 = 0.9213 \text{ (mm/N)}, \quad \chi(\text{Eqn.5}) = 1.03, \quad \chi_o(\text{FE}) = 2.36, \quad \chi_o(\text{Eqn.1}) = 2.46$$

a(mm)	C (mm/N)	χ_{FE} (Eqn.4)	$G_{\text{II(FE)}}$	G_{II} (Eqn.5&6) (N/mm) $\times 10^{-2}$
2.	0.9215	0.696	0.0134	0.014
5.	0.9234	0.904	0.054	0.056
10.	0.9347	0.950	0.183	0.186
20.	1.0160	1.015	0.672	0.677
30.	1.2260	1.024	1.466	1.474
40.	1.6280	1.066	2.567	2.577
50.	2.2820	1.089	3.972	3.987
55.	2.7220	1.090	4.752	4.806

where $G_{\text{II(FE)}}$ is the FE J-integral result.

Table.2 J-integral values

Computations: material constants are the same as those in Table.1 with a=20.0 mm.

Contour No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
J values	.693	.675	.676	.676	.675	.675	.674	.674	.673	.673	.673	.673	.672	.672	.672

Table.3 Correction factor for various materials (ELS specimen)Computations: a=20. (mm) L=60.0 (mm) h=1.0 (mm) B=1.0 (mm) P=1.0 (N) $\nu_{12} = 0.3$

a_{11} (GPa) ⁻¹ x10 ⁻³	a_{22}	a_{66}	χ_{FE} (Eqn.4)	χ (Eqn.5) (N/mm)x10 ⁻²	$G_{II(FE)}$	G_{II} (Eqn.5&6) (18K=11)	$\chi_{o(FE)}$	χ_o (Eqn.1)
6.8	128.	20.	0.33	0.35	0.647	0.634	0.95	0.84
		181.	0.73	0.78	0.661	0.662	1.79	1.88
		362.	1.02	1.03	0.672	0.677	2.36	2.46
		724.	1.36	1.38	0.697	0.700	3.08	3.31
		1448.	1.88	1.89	0.727	0.735	3.89	4.54
		5000.	3.47	3.45	0.877	0.842	5.81	8.33
13.6	128.	20.	0.23	0.25	1.283	1.256	0.75	0.61
		181.	0.55	0.58	1.340	1.295	1.31	1.39
		362.	0.74	0.75	1.347	1.318	1.74	1.80
		724.	1.00	1.00	1.384	1.350	2.33	2.39
		1447.	1.37	1.36	1.438	1.397	3.05	3.26
		5000.	2.49	2.45	1.604	1.543	4.60	5.86
13.6	13.6	181.	0.55	0.51	1.317	1.288	1.20	1.22
		362.	0.74	0.69	1.344	1.310	1.65	1.65
		724.	1.00	0.95	1.383	1.344	2.27	2.27
		1448.	1.40	1.32	1.437	1.391	3.02	3.16
3.4	128.	181.	0.99	1.06	0.347	0.340	2.45	2.55
		362.	1.35	1.46	0.360	0.352	3.15	3.50
		724.	1.91	1.92	0.379	0.378	3.94	4.60
		1448.	2.65	2.66	0.407	0.393	4.88	6.37

Table.4 Comparison of G_{II} values by FE analysis (ELS specimen)Computations: L=60. (mm) $\nu_{12} = 0.3$

$$a_{11}=6.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ (GPa)}^{-1}, \quad a_{22}=128. \times 10^{-3} \text{ (GPa)}^{-1}, \quad a_{66}=362. \times 10^{-3} \text{ (GPa)}^{-1}$$

a (mm)	G_{II} (N/mm)x10 ⁻²			
	by dC/da (fitting)	J-integral	Crack closure	by $\Delta C/\Delta a$ ($\Delta a=0.5$ mm)
10.0	0.190	0.183	0.188	0.190
20.0	0.689	0.672	0.687	0.700
30.0	1.483	1.466	1.519	1.505

Table.5 FEA results (ENF specimen)

Geometry: L=50. (mm) B=1.0 (mm) h=1.5 (mm) P=1.0 (N)

Material: $a_{11} = a_{22} = 7.69 \times 10^{-3} \text{ (GPa)}^{-1}$, $a_{66} = 250. \times 10^{-3} \text{ (GPa)}^{-1}$ $\nu_{12} = 0.3$
 $\chi \text{ (Eqn.5)} = 0.76$, $C_o = 0.074 \text{ (mm/N)}$, $\chi_o \text{ (FE)} = 0.43$

a (mm)	C (mm/N)	$\chi_{FE} \text{ (Eqn.8)}$	$G_{II} \text{ (FE)}$	$G_{II} \text{ (Eqn.8\&5)} \times 10^{-3} \text{ (N/mm)}$
10.	0.075	0.786	0.163	0.160
20.	0.082	0.765	0.597	0.573
30.	0.100	0.807	1.293	1.243
40.	0.134	0.830	2.230	2.170

Material: $a_{11} = 6.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ (GPa)}^{-1}$, $a_{22} = 128. \times 10^{-3} \text{ (GPa)}^{-1}$, $a_{66} = 362. \times 10^{-3} \text{ (GPa)}^{-1}$
 $\nu_{12} = 0.3$
 $\chi \text{ (Eqn.5)} = 1.03$, $C_o = 0.068 \text{ (mm/N)}$, $\chi_o \text{ (FE)} = 0.87$

a (mm)	C (mm/N)	$\chi_{FE} \text{ (Eqn.7)}$	$G_{II} \text{ (FE)}$	$G_{II} \text{ (Eqn.8\&5)} \times 10^{-3} \text{ (N/mm)}$
10.	0.068876	1.15	0.151	0.151
20.	0.075197	1.018	0.551	0.526
30.	0.091374	1.027	1.182	1.128
40.	0.121900	1.037	2.025	1.957

L=50.0 mm a=20.0 mm h=1.5 mm $\nu_{12} = 0.3$

a_{11} a_{22} a_{66} $\chi_{FE} \text{ (Eqn.7)}$ $\chi \text{ (Eqn.5)}$ $G_{II} \text{ (FE)}$ $G_{II} \text{ (Eqn.8\&5)}$
 $C_{o(FE)}$ $\chi_{o(FE)}$ $\chi_o \text{ (Eqn.1)}$
 $\times 10^{-3} \text{ (GPa)}^{-1}$ $\times 10^{-3} \text{ (N/mm)}$ (mm/N)

6.8	128.	181.	0.744	0.784	0.527	0.508	.06564	0.53	1.88
		362.	1.018	1.030	0.551	0.526	.06766	0.87	2.46
		724.	1.415	1.383	0.587	0.552	.07157	1.52	3.31
		1448.	1.967	1.899	0.637	0.592	.07918	2.62	4.54
		5000.	3.468	3.450	0.783	0.719	.1153	7.41	8.33

**Table.6 Experimental compliances of ENF tests C (mm/N) $\times 10^{-3}$
and computed χ values (Eqn.5 gives $\chi = 0.7$)**

test No.	a (mm)	0.0	15.	20.	25.	30.	35.	40.	χ
1		3.236	3.451	3.652	4.192	4.512	5.136	5.930	0.762
2		3.033	3.119	3.333	3.586	4.051	4.521	5.255	-0.110
3		3.145	3.328	3.501	3.868	4.174	4.946	5.612	0.410
4		2.974	3.188	3.344	3.610	4.042	4.826	5.343	0.683
5		3.212	3.405	3.682	3.912	4.408	5.114	5.916	0.931
6		3.149	3.335	3.507	3.797	4.351	5.023	5.824	0.763
7		3.191	3.302	3.407	3.779	4.191	4.888	5.475	0.02
8		3.193	3.366	3.568	3.859	4.300	4.883	5.543	-0.188
9		3.055	3.246	3.409	3.652	4.145	4.755	5.458	0.410
10		3.032	3.252	3.357	3.451	4.215	4.793	5.634	1.263
11		2.970	3.167	3.465	3.778	4.164	4.875	5.430	0.876
12		3.019	3.156	3.339	3.578	3.959	4.561	5.139	-0.494

(a) The End Loaded Split (ELS) Test

(b) The End Notch Flexure (ENF) Test

Fig.1 Mode II Test Configurations